

EXPLORING CONSUMER BEHAVIOR POST COVID USING NICOSIA MODEL FOR A ROMANIAN BERRIES PRODUCER

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Abstract

Purpose – The main goal of this study was to investigate the consumer behavior post Covid for the berries. The interest for a healthy diet increased a lot after pandemic.

Methodology/approach – Nicosia model was used in order to investigate the consumer behavior. It was chosen because its assumption is that the consumer does not have a previous experience with the company and is no predisposition in the buying process.

Findings – The study revealed an insufficient marketing activity, the lack of advertising and the existence of unexplored characteristics of the products and services provided by the company.

Research limitations/implications – The usage of this model does not provide data of the characteristics which may mark customer personality. More information must be included and additional research has to be done in order to help the company to comprehend how the buyer settled his attitude towards the product.

Practical implications – The results of this study reveal the weak points of berry producer. The lack of packaging diversification, lack of an obvious logo on the casseroles and insufficient added services may determine the potential consumers not to buy.

Originality/value – The implementation of consumer behavior models in the market activity of berries producer will increase his competitiveness. The model is quite easy to be applied and does not require too much funds. The opinions of consumer represent a good feedback for the producer.

Key words: consumer behavior, feedback, Nicosia model

Food habits in Romania the context of Covid pandemic

The buyer and consumption behavior of Romanians was strongly affected by Covid pandemic. The demand for food products increased, especially for the nonperishable. An unhealthy eating behavior was developed due to lockdown, low stress control and changes in the income. (McKinsey, 2020). The food consumed at home replaced the consumption in the restaurants and other public places. The grocery stores noticed a thirty percent increased of online shopping. (Chenarides et al, 2021).

The Romanian food market registered the same trends as the global market. Convenience and availability became two important decision factors for the buying process. The election of local producers and higher expenditure for essential products was also noted. The importance of price remained the same for consumers. The online orders had a very rapid growth, both in urban and rural areas. Home delivery was a solution for companies' survival. This trend will continue for the next interval. The importance of brand and sustainability decreased. Logistical challenges and problems in the retail sector occurred. (Pricopie, R. et al, 2021)

The share of fresh food increased in comparison with the packed food. The imported products were bought less than the local products. The consumption of potatoes, sugar, sweeteners, eggs and fish decreased in 2020 in comparison with 2019. Meat, vegetables and nuts consumption increased. Transportation difficulties and labor shortage generated a decrease of the consumption of fresh fruit, but was compensated by frozen and canned vegetables. The acquisition criteria after pandemic in Romanian market are quality, price and home delivery. (Carstoiu, 2020). The new consumption patterns

show a different buying behavior generated by pandemic. Producers and retailers who want a better competitiveness must adapt at the new patterns.

Romanian berry market

The fruit market is important for human health. World Health Organization recommends a daily consumption of more than four hundred grams of fruits and vegetables. A report of RetailZoom revealed that “fruits and vegetables were in top five bestselling categories in modern retail. Fruits were sold according to value nineteen percent more than vegetables and thirty-four percent more in volume”. The sector is listed among the one with high investment opportunities. Romania has EUR 6.2 billion provisioned for rural development in the period 2021-2027 through the European Programs.

The fruits are perishable products which requires specific conditions for packaging, storage, transportation. The berries market registered a high development worldwide in the last years. Europe is ranked in the second position from the point of view of imports, after USA. Many European countries extend their berries crops. Romania has the same trend.

Romania has more than 200 hectares cultivated with berries, but the surface is continuously increased. The bad aspect is the small scale production, the majority of plantations being between ten and forty hectares. Many producers intend to expand them at one hundred hectares. It is considered the possibility to reach the 1500 hectares, according with soil analysis. (Chimielewski, 2016). The investment in new plantations is funded either by government or by European Union with a contribution of fifty percent.

Due to climate characteristics, the harvest season for these fruits starts in June and ends in September, and is longer than in other western countries. One more competitive advantage of Romanian producers is the cheap labor cost. The deficiency of seasonal workers is a great weak aspect. Another problem is related with the packaging required for sales in supermarkets and in international markets. The most common standardized packages for the fruits are in 125 gram, 250 gram and one kilo container. Boxes of three kilo capacities are also used. (italianberry.it, 2020) On the other hand, much attention has to be given to the sorting processes and discarding of damaged or undersized fruits. In order the fruits to be correctly packed are required investments in high productivity equipment. This will allow a better correlation with the increase of production and with the dynamic changes in demand. Machineries provide also an influence on cost factors, decreasing labor cost and increasing efficiency. Some of the producers are organized in groups or cooperatives in order to provide a better reaction for the market requirements.

Much interest is directed on the factors which impact the consumer choice and behavior concerning berry products. (Laksonen, et al, 2016). A comparative study was done for Romania, France and Turkey. The main factors which determine the choice consumption for berries in Romania are: naturalness of the product, taste, price, store availability, local origin, health, extended expiration, organic certification, recommendations, sales promotions and commercials. (Geicu, M. et al, 2017).

The low income from Romania and Turkey determines a frequently irregular consumption of berries. More than half of the interviewed persons declared they agree together with somebody else what type of products will buy. The frequency of buying is weekly or more often and the prefer place for berry shopping is the grocery store. The Romanians enjoy to make food shopping in supermarkets and hypermarkets. The traditional market is ranked in the second position of preferences. The responsibility for shopping returns to the women. The Romanian preferences for berry based products are: berries jams and marmalade, dried berries mixed with cereals, dairy products mixed with berries, frozen berries and fresh berries. The lowest preference is for smoothies and soft drinks.

French consumers take into consideration product naturalness, taste, store availability, price, health, organic certification and extended expiration. The advertisement does not influence them too much and also they do not consider other persons recommendation. If the berries do not have a local provenience, the fruits are considered less fresh and less healthy and the high price is not justified.

The best consumers for berries are persons with higher education, with revenues greater than the average, who live in urban areas and who are concerned about their health. The Romanian market is still restrained and constrained by the economic elements. The producers must take measures in order

to educate potential consumers about the health benefits of berries consumption. To improve the shelf life of the fruits in the market is another concern.

Methodology - Nicosia Model

The Nicosia model was selected for describing the customer behavior of berries buyers. The reason of this selection was the fact that model is a dynamic one and the process can be described as a flowchart and the influences course a circular flow. An element provides input to the following element. The company affects the potential customer, he marks the future actions of the organization and his nowadays behavior affects his future behavior.

There are many models used in the study of consumer behavior. Nicosia model is a structural model because it illustrates the static relationships which occurs among its elements. The model was proposed in 1976 by Nicosia Francesco. The novelty of this model consist of the shift done from the purchasing act to the decision process which involves the customer engagement It is considered as a two ways communication model because the organization send a message to the potential customer and in the second phase, the potential shopper provides a feedback to the company. (NerdySeal, 2021).

The process of the purchase decision making can be described with Nicosia model, from the point of view of marketers. He advocated that the tendency of a potential buyer for a product can be influenced by the advertisement done by the company. The model is based on the relation between the firm and the consumers. The consumers can be approached as an entire family or as an individual consumer. The main assumption of Nicosia model is that the consumer doesnot have any previous experience with this company and no history behind. The mind of the potential shopper doesn't not include a positive or a negative tendency toward the product.

It is a continuous relation between the potential buyer and the organization. The marketing activities of the company are done with the goal of influencing potential buyers and transform them in customers and later, through loyalty programs in clients. The potential buyer has an initial position regarding the product or the service promoted by the organization. If he is enough persuaded he searches additional information about the product and its features. If the information received in this stage is satisfying the potential buyer, he continue the process and decides to buy the product. A negative impact of this stage will have as result the rejection of the product. (Surendra, 2018)

The model helps researchers to reveal the path from attitude establishment to the actual behavior of consumer. The behavior is not always predicted by the attitudes. The relations described by the model are not cause – effects relation. They have to be seen more as a flow of problem solving. The potential buyer gains new experience by bearing in mind, selecting, acquiring and using a new product. The consumers' behavior affects his forthcoming conduct.

The major components of Nicosia model are: the characteristics of the organization, its statements and the psychological features of the potential buyer; the consumers' exploration for estimation of choices; consumers' driven action of acquisition; consumer usage of the product.

The consumer decision is illustrated as a flow chart. This flow chart presents the elements involved and the bond between them. The Nicosia model has four key fields. The first field presents the consumer attitude determined by the messages received from the company. The second field illustrates the exploration and assessment stage, the third one is dedicated to the acquisition act and the fourth field is related with the feedback process. Nicosia model is illustrated in the Figure 1.

The first field of the model takes account of altogether processes which takes the message from the organization to the consumer. It shows how the consumer designs his approach concerning products and services based on the manner of how he receives and translate the message. It has to subfields: one is dedicated to the product features and the second subfield presents the consumer characteristics, especially his predisposition. The marketing background of the firm and its communication efforts are included in the first subfield. The output of the first field is the consumer attitude.

The second field presents the direct reaction to the communication and is a so-called pre-action field. This field is dedicated to the search and evaluation stage, having as starting point the attitude established in the first field. The potential buyer will compare the analyzed brand with other competitor brands. Additional alternatives are listed and considered. If the company provided a good and

convincing communication, the potential customer is motivated to buy the provided product or the service.

Figure 1: Nicosia model (Source www.ebookbou.edu.bd)

The motivation to buy is the output of second field and the input of third field. In the third field, the incentive to buy is converted in the action of purchasing. The act of acquisition leads to a convinced purchasing behavior.

The fourth field is dedicated to the feedback which occurs after the acquisition. The feedback is considered at both level: company level and customer level. The customer feedback becomes a new input for the company. It will redesign the message and the marketing policies in order to provide a better motivation for future buyers. The customer will have experience retention which will influence his future buying processes.

Applying Nicosia model for a Romanian berries producer

The pandemic made many changes in the buying behavior of food products. A higher concern for a healthy diet was noticed. People try to create a strong immunity in order to be protected as much as possible by Covid. They try to embrace a well-adjusted nutrition and a healthy existence. Older age groups were more concerned than the young groups. The studies revealed an increase in buying fresh fruits and vegetables. The berries producers benefit from this trend.

This investigation was done for a small berry producer from Bistrita County. His plantation was established six years ago and its surface is half hectare. The number of plants for this year was 1800. He decided to plant berries because they have a higher resistance at lower temperature, and the area where is located the plantation is a quite cold one. Another advantage is that this plant helps farmers to better use land with lower quality. The plantation does not have an irrigation system, aspect which imposes additional watering and causes decreased production. The size of the fruits is smaller because of the droughts.

The packaging is done in casseroles of small volume. The required quantity for home delivery is five kilos, because of high prices of fuel. The orders are delivered in the town or in a maximum 30 kilometers

distance. The price per kilo was about three euro. The rest of production is sold in small shops. A collaboration with supermarkets was desired but the quantity of the crop is too smaller to allow one to assure a continuous delivery at the required quantity.

The company done little marketing activities. The advertisement is done more through social media, especially by Facebook. The central message is based on the freshness of the fruits, the local provenience and the home delivery under some circumstances.

The first field of Nicosia model contains the following attributes: quality, freshness, local provenience and convenient delivery. If the analysis was done from the point of view of potential buyer, it was discovered that he cares more about the taste, the freshness and the price. The Nicosia model assumption that the customer does not have any knowledge or previous contact with this company was respected. The assumption of not knowing the product cannot be totally accomplished because all people know berries, but they did not know the visual aspect, the variety, the taste and the ratio price / quality. Majority of the customer mentioned as being important to support the local producers and the buy food from their area. This offers the guarantee of freshness and quality in their opinion. They suggested a diversification of packages from the point of view of the volume. Many considered to be useful for consumer to have a personalized pack and to include a logo of the company in order to be easy to identify in the shell. The insufficient advertisement was mentioned as a weak point.

The second field of Nicosia model is related with attitude and motivation. The customers consider different alternatives from different producers. They do not have a real image of which alternative brand or variety of berries are available. They associate more the other buying option with the shop which sell the berries. Only few of them read the labels and know information about the fruits they buy. More information is known about vegetables sold in Carrefour chain, because the hypermarket invested a lot in order to teach potential customers about its collaboration with Romanian producers. If are compared our berries with let's say "Carrefour berries", the conclusions are: the local producer brand is underestimated in comparison with the one from hypermarket, the freshness is considered better than the one from the big chain, the hypermarket has special offers and loyalty programs and the small producer cannot provide this, the local producer delivers home free for bigger quantities while Carrefour has some delivery constrains.

Third field converts the incentive to buy in the buying process. The potential buyer behaved as the previous researches revealed and made the acquisition decision for food and berries after discussions and recommendation of other persons. Their decision is also supported by the hope of keeping the path to a healthy style of life. About half of the persons who decided to buy the berries recognized that they rarely include fresh berries in the diet. It is more common for them to consume dry berries mixed with cereals or different types of chocolate products with berries.

In the fourth field, the consumer express his opinion after he bought and ate the berries. The buyer will tell the positive and negative characteristics from his point of view. His opinion influences other potential customers. The producer must collect this information and use it as a new input for his future actions. If a consumer is not satisfied, the company will try to isolate him in order not to remove others.

Discussion and conclusions

Nicosia model was applied for a Romanian berry producer. Quality, freshness, local provenience and convenient delivery are the main features considered by a potential consumer. In spite of the real qualities of the fruits, the consumers are more motivated by marketing activities of big supermarkets chains. There are required some changes in the market approach. A diversification of the packages from the volume point of view, the addition of company logo and a decrease of home delivery constrains are some of the proposed measures for short time horizon.

In medium and long run, the producer must implement dripping irrigation systems, plant new varieties of berries (example: Loch Ness) with higher productivity and a longer fructification interval. The new varieties of barriers plants grow straight and the harvesting process is much easier. In addition the distance between rows and between plants is smaller.

Last but not least, a better advertising is mandatory. Collaboration with cake shops, bakeries and companies which organize events for the children can increase the economical results.

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